

AN ADVANCED 1D FINITE ELEMENT SOLUTION FOR THERMOELASTICITY PROBLEMS IN LAMINATED BEAMS

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Keywords: Thermoelasticity, Laminated beams, CUF, FEM

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the present work is the evaluation of the effects of a number of parameters on the static and dynamic thermoelastic responses of laminated beams. In particular, the stacking sequence, the aspect-ratio, the degree of anisotropy, the boundary and loading conditions are considered as problem parameters. To this end, higher-order one-dimensional models are developed for thermoelastic analyses. Governing equations (equations of motion and energy equation) are derived in a unified manner. The developed unified formulation enables the dynamic and static classical coupled and uncoupled theories of thermoelasticity to be obtained. The equations, which are written in the weak form using the weighted residual method based on the Galerkin technique, are derived according to the Carrera Unified Formulation (CUF) and the Finite Element (FE) Method. The used methodology reduces the 3D problem to one-dimensional models that are able to provide 3D-like solutions with a relevant level of accuracy. Moreover, the classical coupled, dynamic uncoupled, quasi-static uncoupled, and steady-state uncoupled theories of thermoelasticity can be derived as particular cases.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the second half of the last century, the advanced design problems have brought many researchers to propose reliable and computationally effective methods to study the interactions between elastic and temperature fields. These interactions can appear in many applications such as aerospace structures, fast-burst reactors, and particle accelerators. When a structure is exposed to high-speed thermo-mechanical loads, the thermoelastic interactions may be simulated using the theories of coupled thermoelasticity to provide entirely true physical behaviors. In these theories, the time derivatives of strain appear in the heat conduction equation so as to lead to the coupling between elasticity and energy equations. Accordingly, to find the solution for temperature and displacement fields and finally stresses, these coupled equations must be solved concurrently.

The equations for a coupled thermoelastic beam, including the effects of shear deformation and rotatory inertia, are derived by Jones [1]. Coupled thermally induced vibrations of Euler–Bernoulli and Timoshenko beams with one-dimensional heat conduction are investigated by Seibert and Rice [2]. The analytical solutions of the coupled thermoelasticity of beams made of homogeneous and isotropic materials based on Euler–Bernoulli and Timoshenko assumptions were provided in references [3] and [4], respectively. In the treatment of these problems a linear approximation for temperature variation across the thickness direction of the beam is considered. Abbasi et al. [5] presented the analytical solution for a beam made of a functionally graded material (FGM) based on first order shear deformation theory. They utilized the finite Fourier transformation method along with the analytical Laplace inverse procedure to solve the governing equations.

In general, analytical solutions of the coupled thermoelasticity problems are mathematically laborious, so that many simplifying assumptions may be required to achieve a closed form solution for such problems. Accordingly, the development of alternative solution techniques including semi-analytical and numerical methods has been essential. In order to obtain numerical solution of the coupled thermoelastic problems, the finite difference (FD), the finite element (FE) and the boundary

element (BE) methods have been used. Among these procedures, however, the FE method is more widely employed for this class of problems due to its adaptability.

Eslami and Vahedi presented the one-dimensional coupled thermoelasticity problem of rods with classical coupled assumption using the Galerkin FE method [6]. Finite element coupled thermoelastic analysis of composite Timoshenko beams is given by Maruthi and Sinha [7], where the temperature variation across the thickness direction is neglected. Manoach and Ribeiro developed a numerical procedure to study the coupled large amplitude thermoelastic vibrations of Timoshenko beams subjected to the thermal and mechanical loads using the finite difference approximation and modal coordinate transformations [8]. Sankar solved the elastic problem of FGM beam and computed the thermal stresses in an FGM Euler-beam based on the uncoupled thermoelasticity assumption [9, 10]. Chakraborty et al. [11] presented a FE formulation for dynamic uncoupled thermoelasticity in functionally graded beam structures based on the first-order shear deformation theory. In this paper, a beam element was developed to obtain a convergence stiffness matrix and eliminate the shear locking effect of the element. Using Galerkin FE method, Babaei et al. [12] rendered a 1D classical thermoelasticity solution for an Euler–Bernoulli beam made of FGM. Using a semi-analytical FE method, Afshar et al. [13] obtained 2D coupled thermoelasticity solution for a simply supported beam made of FGM. They combined the method of finite Fourier series with the Galerkin FE method to solve the 2D coupled equations.

In more practical problems, the geometry of structures as well as boundary and loading conditions are complex. Furthermore, in recent years, advanced new materials are used in modern structures under thermo-mechanical shock loads, so that, the 1D and 2D FE models are not able to provide all the desired information. Accordingly, the 3D FE modeling techniques may be required for a detailed coupled thermoelastic analysis in such cases.

Notwithstanding substantial advances in the field of computing power, a 3D FE model still imposes large computational costs, especially during a time-consuming transient solution of the coupled thermoelastic problems. This can explain why there is a growing interest in the development of advanced FE models to 3D solution of such problems with lower computational efforts.

The main aim of the present paper is to render an advanced 1D FE solution for thermoelasticity problems in laminated beams. For this purpose, the Galerkin technique is applied to obtain a weak formulation of the thermoelasticity problems. The FE approach in framework of the 1D Carrera unified formulation (CUF) for the coupled thermoelastic problems is briefly presented. Accordingly, the FE matrices are obtained in CUF form, which are called fundamental nuclei. For the dynamic problems, the governing coupled equations are solved in the Laplace transform domain by the FE method and then the transformed solutions are numerically inverted to find the physical time domain response. Some numerical results are presented and, when possible, compared with those available in the literature.

2. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The equation of motion for a 3D elastic body in the physical coordinate system (x, y, z) is stated as follows [14]

$$\sigma_{ij,j} + X_i = \rho \ddot{u}_i \quad (1)$$

Where σ_{ij} and u_i are stress and displacement components, respectively. X_i denotes body forces per unit volume and ρ is mass density. Likewise, the superscript dot ($\dot{}$) and the subscript comma ($,$) indicate the derivatives with respect to the time (t) and the space variables (xyz), respectively.

In addition, the strain-displacement relations within the linear context of small deformation theory are expressed as [14]

$$\epsilon_{ij} = (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i})/2 \quad (2)$$

and Hooke's law for a nonhomogeneous anisotropic thermoelastic material can be written as [14]

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijpq} \varepsilon_{pq} - T \beta_{ij} \quad (3)$$

where C_{ijpq} is a fourth-order tensor containing all the elastic coefficients of a general nonhomogeneous anisotropic material. $\beta_{ij} = C_{ijpq} \alpha_{pq}$ is the second order tensor of thermoelastic moduli where in α_{ij} is the coefficient of thermal expansion tensor. In Eq. (3), T denotes the temperature change relative to the reference temperature T_0 , so that this temperature difference creates thermal strain.

Likewise, the energy equation can be expressed in terms of the temperature and displacement fields as [14]

$$\rho c \dot{T} - (\kappa_{ij} T_{,j})_{,i} + T_0 \beta_{ij} \dot{u}_{i,j} = R \quad (4)$$

Equations (1) and (4) constitute the governing system of equations for the classical coupled thermoelasticity problems in an anisotropic and nonhomogeneous medium. Thus, the four coupled equations, including three equations of motion and one heat conduction equation, under specified initial and boundary conditions must be simultaneously solved for the three unknown displacement components (u_i) and the one unknown temperature change (T).

3. GALERKIN FINITE ELEMENT TECHNIQUE

To obtain a weak form formulation of the governing equations (1) and (4), Galerkin technique may be utilized. In implementation of the conventional FE method, the 3D domain with the volume V can be discretized into a finite number of regular 3D solid elements. Thus, the components of displacement and temperature change in each base element can be approximated by identical shape functions as follows

$$\begin{aligned} u_i^{(e)}(x, y, z, t) &= \phi_m(x, y, z) U_i^m(t) \\ T^{(e)}(x, y, z, t) &= \phi_m(x, y, z) \Theta^m(t) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where U_i^m and Θ^m are the displacement vector and the temperature change at each nodal point of the element. $\phi_m(x, y, z)$ denotes shape functions in the base element. It is noted that in these approximations, time and space variables are separated into distinct functions. Furthermore, the repeated subscript $m = 1, \dots, r$ is a dummy index and indicates summation while r stands for the number of nodal points in the element [14].

According to Galerkin method, multiplying both sides of Eq. (1) by the shape functions $\phi_m(x, y, z)$ and then integrating over volume of the element, yields

$$\int_{V^{(e)}} (\sigma_{ij,j} + X_i - \rho \ddot{u}_i) \phi_m dV = 0 \quad (6)$$

Applying the divergence theorem and then using the relationship between the traction vector (t_i^n) acting on an arbitrary surface (S) and the stress tensor, Eq. (6) can be expressed as

$$\int_{V^{(e)}} (\rho \ddot{u}_i \phi_m) dV + \int_{V^{(e)}} (\phi_{m,j} \sigma_{ij}) dV = \int_{V^{(e)}} X_i \phi_m dV + \int_{S^{(e)}} t_i^n \phi_m dS \quad (7)$$

Similarly, applying Galerkin method to the energy equation (4) and using the divergence theorem gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{V^{(e)}} (T_0 \beta_{ij} \dot{u}_{i,j} \phi_m) dV + \int_{V^{(e)}} (\rho c \dot{T} \phi_m) dV + \int_{V^{(e)}} (\kappa_{ij} T_{,j} \phi_{m,i}) dV \\
 & = \int_{S^{(e)}} (q_i n_i \phi_m) dS + \int_{V^{(e)}} (R \phi_m) dV
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Equations (7) and (8) represent the general weak formulation containing all possible boundary conditions for the classical coupled thermoelasticity problems. The system of equations (7) and (8) as well as the stress-strain relations (3) may be expressed in vector form as

$$\int_{V^{(e)}} (\rho \ddot{\mathbf{u}} \phi_m) dV + \int_{V^{(e)}} (\mathbf{D}^T \phi_m \boldsymbol{\sigma}) dV = \int_{V^{(e)}} (\mathbf{X} \phi_m) dV + \int_{S^{(e)}} (\mathbf{t} \phi_m) dS \tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{V^{(e)}} (T_0 \boldsymbol{\beta}^T \mathbf{D} \dot{\mathbf{u}} \phi_m) dV + \int_{V^{(e)}} (\rho c \dot{T} \phi_m) dV + \int_{V^{(e)}} (\nabla^T T \boldsymbol{\kappa} \nabla \phi_m) dV \\
 & = \int_{S^{(e)}} (\mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{n} \phi_m) dS + \int_{V^{(e)}} (R \phi_m) dV
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - T \boldsymbol{\beta} \tag{11}$$

4. 1D CUF FOR THE COUPLED THERMOELASTICITY

Consider a structure subjected to thermo-mechanical shock loads which is located in the rectangular Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) . If the structure can be assumed as a beam along the y -direction, each cross section of the beam is defined in the xz -plane and perpendicular to the y -axis.

Within the 1D CUF and FEM frameworks [15], the primary variables (the three displacement components of $\mathbf{u}(x, y, z, t)$ vector and the temperature field $T(x, y, z, t)$) are being written as it follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{u}(x, y, z, t) &= N_m(y) F_\tau(x, z) \mathbf{U}^{m\tau}(t) & m = 1, \dots, NB \\
 T(x, y, z, t) &= N_m(y) F_\tau(x, z) \Theta^{m\tau}(t) & \tau = 1, \dots, NL
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where $\mathbf{U}^{m\tau}(t)$ is the generalized displacement vector, and $\Theta^{m\tau}(t)$ is the generalized temperature change at each nodal point. The summation convention is used for the dummy indexes τ and m . The terms $F_\tau(x, z)$ are functions of the cross-section coordinates (x, z) , $N_m(y)$ are the Lagrangian beam shape functions, while NL and NB stand for the number of the terms used in the expansion and the number of nodes for each finite element, respectively.

Thus, comparing the relations (12) with Eq. (5) results in the following relationship

$$\phi_m(x, y, z) = N_m(y) F_\tau(x, z) \tag{13}$$

5. FE EQUATIONS IN CUF FORM

Substituting relations (12) and (13) into Eqs. (9) and (10) and then rearranging the terms, the following matrix equations is obtained

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{UU}^{lm\tau s} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{M}_{\Theta\Theta}^{lm\tau s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{U}}^{ls} \\ \ddot{\Theta}^{ls} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{G}_{U\Theta}^{lm\tau s} \\ \mathbf{G}_{\Theta U}^{lm\tau s} & \mathbf{G}_{\Theta\Theta}^{lm\tau s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{U}}^{ls} \\ \dot{\Theta}^{ls} \end{Bmatrix} \\
 & + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{UU}^{lm\tau s} & \mathbf{K}_{U\Theta}^{lm\tau s} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}_{\Theta\Theta}^{lm\tau s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{U}^{ls} \\ \Theta^{ls} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{F}^{ls} \\ \mathbf{Q}^{ls} \end{Bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

here, the indexes s and l are similar to τ and m , respectively, and indicate summation. Equation (14) renders the 1D unified finite element formulation which can be employed to 3D analysis of the classical coupled thermoelastic problems. The presented approach enables all the FE matrix and vectors to derive as a condensed notation which is named the so-called fundamental nucleus (FN). Indeed, these fundamental nuclei do not depend on either the order of the expansion or the base functions used. The FN of the mass, damping and stiffness matrices as well as of the load vector can be expressed as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\mathbf{M}_{UU}^{lm\tau s}]_{3 \times 3} &= \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (\rho N_m N_l \mathbf{I} F_\tau F_s) dAdL \\
 [\mathbf{M}_{\Theta\Theta}^{lm\tau s}]_{1 \times 1} &= \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (\rho c t_2 N_m N_l F_\tau F_s) dAdL
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\mathbf{G}_{U\Theta}^{lm\tau s}]_{3 \times 3} &= - \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} ((\mathbf{D}_{np}^T F_\tau \mathbf{I}) \beta_n] F_s) dAdL \\
 [\mathbf{G}_{\Theta U}^{lm\tau s}]_{1 \times 3} &= \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (T_0 N_m N_l [\beta_p^T (\mathbf{D}_p F_s) + \beta_n^T (\mathbf{D}_{np} F_s)] F_\tau) dAdL \\
 &+ \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (T_0 [\beta_n^T N_m (\mathbf{D}_{ny} N_l) F_s F_\tau]) dAdL \\
 [\mathbf{G}_{\Theta\Theta}^{lm\tau s}]_{1 \times 1} &= \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (\rho c N_m N_l F_\tau F_s) dAdL
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\mathbf{K}_{UU}^{lm\tau s}]_{3 \times 3} &= \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (N_m N_l [(\mathbf{D}_{np}^T F_\tau \mathbf{I}) [\mathbf{C}_{mn} (\mathbf{D}_{np} F_s \mathbf{I}) + \mathbf{C}_{np} (\mathbf{D}_p F_s \mathbf{I})] \\
 &+ (\mathbf{D}_p^T F_\tau \mathbf{I}) [\mathbf{C}_{pp} (\mathbf{D}_p F_s \mathbf{I}) + \mathbf{C}_{pn} (\mathbf{D}_{np} F_s \mathbf{I})]]) dAdL \\
 &+ \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (N_m (\mathbf{D}_{ny} N_l) [(\mathbf{D}_{np}^T F_\tau \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{C}_{mn} + (\mathbf{D}_p^T F_\tau \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{C}_{pn}] F_s) dAdL \\
 &+ \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} ((\mathbf{D}_{ny}^T N_m) N_l F_\tau [\mathbf{C}_{np} (\mathbf{D}_p F_s \mathbf{I}) + \mathbf{C}_{mn} (\mathbf{D}_{np} F_s \mathbf{I})]) dAdL \\
 &+ \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} ((\mathbf{D}_{ny}^T N_m) (\mathbf{D}_{ny} N_l) F_\tau \mathbf{C}_{m s}) dAdL \\
 [\mathbf{K}_{U\Theta}^{lm\tau s}]_{3 \times 1} &= - \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (N_m N_l [(\mathbf{D}_p^T F_\tau) \beta_p + (\mathbf{D}_{np}^T F_\tau) \beta_n] F_s) dAdL \\
 &- \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} ((\mathbf{D}_{ny}^T N_m) N_l F_\tau \beta_n F_s) dAdL \\
 [\mathbf{K}_{\Theta\Theta}^{lm\tau s}]_{1 \times 1} &= \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (N_m N_l (\nabla_p^T F_s) \kappa (\nabla_p F_\tau)) dAdL \\
 &+ \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} ((\nabla_n^T N_l) (N_m) \kappa (\nabla_p F_\tau) F_s) dAdL \\
 &+ \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (N_l (\nabla_n N_m) \kappa (\nabla_p F_s) F_\tau) dAdL \\
 &+ \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} ((\nabla_n^T N_l) (\nabla_n N_m) F_\tau \kappa F_s) dAdL
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{\mathbf{F}^{m\tau}\}_{3 \times 1} &= \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (\mathbf{X} N_m F_\tau) dAdL + \int_{S^{(e)}} (\mathbf{t} N_m F_\tau) dS \\
 \{\mathbf{Q}^{m\tau}\}_{1 \times 1} &= \int_{S^{(e)}} (\mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{n} N_m F_\tau) dS + \int_{L^{(e)}} \int_{A^{(e)}} (R N_m F_\tau) dAdL
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

In the expressions (15)-(18), \mathbf{I} represents the identity matrix. The subscript p denotes the in-plane components over a cross section of the structure, while n indicates the normal components to the cross section. Accordingly, the matrices \mathbf{D}_p , \mathbf{D}_{np} and \mathbf{D}_{ny} and the vectors ∇_p and ∇_n can be defined as

$$\mathbf{D}_p = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \partial_z \\ \partial_x & 0 & 0 \\ \partial_z & 0 & \partial_x \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{D}_{np} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \partial_z & 0 \\ 0 & \partial_x & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{D}_{ny} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \partial_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \partial_y \\ \partial_y & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

Where $\partial_x = \partial / \partial x$, $\partial_y = \partial / \partial y$ and $\partial_z = \partial / \partial z$. Moreover

$$\nabla_p = \{\partial_x \quad 0 \quad \partial_z\}^T, \quad \nabla_n = \{0 \quad \partial_y \quad 0\}^T \quad (20)$$

Similarly, the grouped elastic coefficients matrix and stress-temperature moduli vector are given as

$$\mathbf{C}_{pp} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{14} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{24} \\ C_{41} & C_{42} & C_{44} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{nm} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{33} & C_{35} & C_{36} \\ C_{53} & C_{55} & C_{56} \\ C_{63} & C_{65} & C_{66} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{pn} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{13} & C_{15} & C_{16} \\ C_{23} & C_{25} & C_{26} \\ C_{43} & C_{45} & C_{46} \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

$$\beta_p = \{\beta_{zz} \quad \beta_{xx} \quad \beta_{xz}\}^T \quad \beta_n = \{\beta_{yy} \quad \beta_{yz} \quad \beta_{xy}\}^T \quad (22)$$

In order to summarize, the expanded expressions for components of the matrix \mathbf{C} for anisotropic materials are not given here, but they can be found in Ref. [16].

Thus, the matrix form of the governing equation for the whole structure can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\Delta} + \mathbf{G}\dot{\Delta} + \mathbf{K}\Delta = \mathbf{P} \quad (23)$$

Where \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{K} are the global mass, damping and stiffness matrices. Likewise, \mathbf{P} is the global vector of the applied mechanical and thermal loads and Δ stands for the global vector of unknowns.

Applying the Laplace method, Eq. (23) is transformed in an algebraic system that is function of the Laplace transform parameter \tilde{s} as

$$\mathbf{K}_{eq}(\tilde{s})\Delta^* = \mathbf{P}^*(\tilde{s}) \quad (24)$$

Where Δ^* and \mathbf{P}^* represent the unknowns and the load vectors in the Laplace domain. \mathbf{K}_{eq} is the equivalent stiffness matrix that includes inertial, stiffness and damping contributions and can be obtained as

$$\mathbf{K}_{eq}(\tilde{s}) = \mathbf{M}\tilde{s}^2 + \mathbf{G}\tilde{s} + \mathbf{K} \quad (25)$$

The linear system of Eq. (24) is then solved for different values of \tilde{s} , and the related results are being expressed in the time-domain using the numerical inversion of Laplace transforms proposed by Durbin [17]. The procedure outlined is used to solve quasi-static as well as dynamic problems according to which loads are considered.

Likewise, for dynamic problems, it may be expedient to solve Eq. (24) in a dimensionless form. To this end, the following parameters are introduced

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{x}_i &= c\sqrt{\rho(\bar{\lambda} + 2\mu)}x_i / \kappa ; \hat{t} = c(\bar{\lambda} + 2\mu)t / \kappa ; \hat{T} = T / T_d ; \\
 \hat{u}_i &= c(\lambda + \mu)\sqrt{\rho(\bar{\lambda} + 2\mu)}u_i / (\kappa\bar{\beta}T_d) ; \hat{q}_i = q_i / cT_d\sqrt{\rho(\bar{\lambda} + 2\mu)} ; \\
 \hat{\sigma}_{ij} &= \sigma_{ij} / (\bar{\beta}T_d) ; \hat{t}_i^n = t_i^n / (T_d\bar{\beta}) ; \\
 \hat{X}_i &= \kappa X_i / (cT_d\bar{\beta}\sqrt{\rho(\bar{\lambda} + 2\mu)}) ; \hat{R} = \kappa R / (c^2\rho T_d(\bar{\lambda} + 2\mu))
 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

where the hat values indicate nondimensional parameters. T_d is a characteristic temperature and the expressions of $\bar{\lambda}$ and $\bar{\beta}$ may be related to the Lamé constants, λ and μ .

6. NUMERICAL APPLICATIONS

To validate the proposed formulation, an isotropic homogeneous beam is considered. The geometrical and the material properties are reported in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Aluminum cantilever beam. Conduction from wall and constant temperature at end of beam.

The beam is subjected to a constant heat flux applied to its clamped end. Its tip is free and the temperature is assumed to be constant. The structure is modelled using Lagrange-type elements (L9) above the cross-section (functions F_T are quadratic functions of x and z coordinates) and different meshes of 2-node beam elements (B2) along the longitudinal direction. Tables 1 and 2 compare the 1D-CUF solutions in terms of axial displacement and temperature change at different locations with the results obtained by using ANSYS software. The comparisons reveal a good agreement between the two approaches.

Location	y (m)	Temperature change			
		1D ANSYS	CUF		
			5B2/1L9	5B2/ 4L9	20B2/ 4L9
1	0.0	105.49	107.43	105.79	105.49
2	0.1	84.34	83.87	84.30	84.38
3	0.2	63.291	63.42	63.31	63.28
4	0.3	42.194	42.15	42.17	42.192
5	0.4	21.097	21.10	21.09	21.096
6	0.5	0	0	0	0

Table 1: Temperature change at different locations.

Location	y (m)	Axial Displacement (mm)			
		1D ANSYS	CUF solution		
			5B2/ 1L9	5B2/4L9	20B2/4L9
1	0.0	0	0	0	0
2	0.1	0.21930	0.30976	0.31570	0.244779
3	0.2	0.38987	0.48296	0.476379	0.41373
4	0.3	0.51171	0.59204	0.59081	0.53677
5	0.4	0.58481	0.67598	0.672862	0.60865
6	0.5	0.60918	0.69345	0.69339	0.63306

Table 2: Axial displacement at different locations.

Since, the current approach is able to provide three-dimensional results, Fig. 2 shows the deformed beam configuration and the distribution of temperature changes within the structure.

Figure 2: Distribution of the axial displacement (a) and the temperature change (b) computed with the 20B2/ 4L9 model.

In the second numerical application, the coupled thermoelastic response of a beam consisting of two layers with same dimensions and made of different isotropic materials has been evaluated. The three-dimensional governing equations have been solved in a dimensionless form. The properties of the considered materials are reported in Table 1. The edge of the square cross-section has a dimensionless length equal to 0.05, while the longitudinal dimension is 0.5. A dimensionless temperature change equal to $\bar{T} = 1 - e^{-\bar{t}}$ has been imposed on the top surface, while the bottom one has been assumed thermally isolated.

Property	Metal	Ceramic
Lame' constant λ	40.4 GPa	80.05 GPa
Lame' constant μ	27 GPa	44.25 GPa
coefficient of linear thermal expansion (α)	$23 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$	$7.11 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$
density (ρ)	2707 kg/m ³	5600 kg/m ³
thermal conductivity (κ)	204 W/m·K	2.036 W/m·K
specific heat (c)	903 J/kg·K	615.6 J/kg·K

Table 3: Material properties.

The structure has been considered supported by two rollers at both ends. The mathematical model consisted of two 9-node Lagrange elements above the cross-section and ten 4-node beam elements along the longitudinal direction. The thermoelastic analyses have been performed considering two lamination sequences that are, starting from the bottom surface, Metal/Ceramic and Ceramic/Metal. Figures 3 shows the time histories of the transverse displacement and the temperature change at the mid-point of the beam according to the classical coupled theory.

Figure 3: Time history of the transverse displacement (a) and the temperature change (b) at the mid-point.

It is observed that the oscillation amplitude of the structure with the top surface made of ceramic material is lower than the oscillation experienced by the Ceramic/Metal configuration. On the other hand, the time histories of the temperature change at the mid-point are practically coincident. In fact, the steady-state value has been reached at the same non-dimensional time ($\bar{t} = 0.5$).

Figures 4 and 5 show the three-dimensional distributions of the temperature changes and the transverse displacements at different times for the Metal/Ceramic beam.

7. CONCLUSION

The proposed unified formulation enables classical and generalized coupled theories of thermoelasticity to be derived. The current approach has been validated through comparisons with results obtained by a commercial code considering static analyses. A laminated beam with two layers, which are made of metallic and ceramic materials, has been studied. For given boundary and loading conditions, it has been observed that the lamination sequence may determine relevant changes in the thermomechanical response. Further analyses will be performed in future works.

Figure 4: Non-dimensional temperature change at different non-dimensional times.

Figure 5: Non-dimensional transverse displacements at different non-dimensional times.

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